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gender equality to unlock
research potential

D6.6 EURAXESS Webinar

Project Acronym: ATHENA

Title: IMPLEMENTING GENDER EQUALITY PLANS TO UNLOCK RESEARCH POTENTIAL OF RPOS AND RFOS IN EUROPE

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¹ PU= Public, CO=Confidential, only for members of the Consortium (including the Commission Services), CL=Classified, as referred in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

C&C	The Charter & Code
HRS4R	The Human Resources Strategy for Researchers
GEP	Gender Equality Plan
GE	Gender equality

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose and scope

One of the ATHENA tasks foresees the establishment of synergies and connections with the EURAXESS initiative. These synergies include the organization of a webinar, entitled 'Gender equality and researchers' mobility – Synergies from EURAXESS initiative' to 1) present the EURAXESS network, and more specifically their two initiatives for researchers: the *Charter & Code (C&C)* and the *Human Resources Strategy for Researchers (HRS4R)*; 2) jointly discuss on the relevance of gender equality measures as element of attractiveness for researchers and to engage them in a mobility experience.

The present document is a note to briefly reports on the EURAXESS Webinar that took place on 20 June 2022.

1.2 Document structure

The document describes:

- 1) The objective of the event and its general description (**section 2**).
- 2) Main event information and figures (**section 3**).
- 3) Display of an event picture (**section 4**).
- 4) How to access the recording of the event (**section 5**).
- 5) Main conclusions (**section 6**).

2. Event objective and description

As above mentioned, within the ATHENA project, specific efforts have been dedicated to establishing a communication and dissemination partnership with EURAXESS. This has been supported by one webinar that was organized on 20 June 2022. During the event, named ‘Gender equality and researchers’ mobility – Synergies form EURAXESS initiative’, the EURAXESS initiative and network were introduced and the areas for collaboration between EURAXESS and ATHENA were discussed. Moreover, the C&C, the two seminal documents established within this initiative, as well as the HRS4R have been a topic of discussion, in particular focussing on how these could inform the design of tailored Gender Equality Plans within the project, especially when it comes to gender non-discrimination and work life balance measures.

Thus, the objective of the event was to **highlight existing and potential synergies between the services of EURAXESS and the implementation of gender equality plans in the ATHENA project and eventually the sister project MINDtheGEPs**. The relevance of gender equality measures were discussed as element of attractiveness to attract researchers and for researchers engaging in a mobility experience.

Key speakers, apart from Michelle Perello, the ATHENA project coordinator, were contacted and invited to attend the webinar:

- Angela Balzano | MINDtheGEPs coordination team member - University of Turin.
- Slaven Misljencevic | EURAXESS Policy Officer – European Commission.
- Michele Rosa-Clot | HRS4R Portfolio manager – European Commission.

The discussion session was enriched with the participation of Ivana Radonova, ATHENA Advisory Board member from the Ministry of Education and Science of Bulgaria, and Mark de Vos, EURAXESS Bridge Head for Denmark.

The agenda of the event may be consulted in the Annex I of the document.

3. Event figures

The table below summarizes the main event information, number of participants and its gender balance:

Table 1. Main event information and number of participants

Title of the event	Gender equality and researchers' ability – synergies from EURAXESS initiative
Date of the event	20/06/2022
Venue of the event	Online via 'ZOOM Webinar'
Names and positions of the speakers and key invited participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Michelle Perello ATHENA coordinator - Consulta Europa Projects and Innovation. • Angela Balzano MINDtheGEPs coordination team member - University of Turin. • Slaven Misljencevic EURAXESS Policy Officer – European Commission. • Michele Rosa-Clot HRS4R Portfolio manager – European Commission. • Ivana Radonova Ministry of Education and Science of Bulgaria. • Mark de Vos EURAXESS Bridge Head for Denmark.
Total of number of participants	<p>Total number of all participants:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 6 - Number of panelists • 62 - Number of participants registered • 48 – Number of participants that attended the event <p>54 – Total number of attendees</p> <p>Attendees by countries:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bulgaria - 11 • Czech Republic – 2 • Spain – 8 • Belgium – 1 • France – 1 • Great Britain – 1 • Ireland – 2 • Italy – 3 • Philippines - 1 • Poland – 2 • Portugal – 6 • Romania – 2 • Slovenia – 6 • Slovakia – 4

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Turkey – 1 • USA – 2
Gender balance of participants	<p>Female – 83,33%</p> <p>Male – 15%</p> <p>Non-binary - 0%</p> <p>Prefer not to say – 1,67%</p>
Participants from the ATHENA institutions	Number: 24

Originally, it was planned to attract 40 participants, belonging to the following organizations:

- ✓ 7 RPOs from ATHENA (staff, researchers and representatives of researchers).
- ✓ 7 RPOs from MINDtheGEPs project (staff, researchers and representatives of researchers).
- ✓ 2 RFOs from ATHENA.
- ✓ Business associations and civil society organizations from ATHENA countries.

Finally and as abovementioned, 54 participants attended the webinar.

4. Picture of the event

Figure 1. Webinar screenshot with the panel of key speakers taken during the discussion session

5. Access to the event recording

The recording of the event is uploaded and publicly shared at the ATHENA YouTube channel. It may be consulted [here](#).

6. Conclusion

The event was considered successful, not only for the number of participants that attended but also for the content of the presentations and the discussion held at the end of the event. The event topic, the connection between researchers' mobility and the gender equality measures, was somewhat unfamiliar not only to many of the project partners, but also to the other participants. The event was an opportunity to introduce these key topics at the same time as become them familiar with the EURAXESS network, the C&C and the HRS4R.

This webinar has been a first step of collaboration with the EURAXESS initiative. Further collaborations are envisaged as the project progresses, e.g. invitation as expert of one of the 3 Mutual Learning Workshops that will be organized, join the ATHENA e-platform.

Annex I – Event agenda

Webinar

Gender equality and researchers' mobility – Synergies from EURAXESS initiative

20 June 2022 | 10.00 CEST time

Online: Zoom. Link to register [here](#)

9.50h – 10.00h	Connect online
10.00h – 10.10h	<p>ATHENA project – Implementing gender equality plans to unlock research potential of RPOs and RFOs in Europe.</p> <p>Michelle Perello ATHENA coordinator - Consulta Europa Projects and Innovation</p>
10.10h – 10.20h	<p>MINDtheGEPs project – Reducing gender imbalances in European research institutions and generating data to support the development of national and European policy for gender equality in RPOs.</p> <p>Angela Balzano MINDtheGEPs coordination team member - University of Turin</p>
10.20h – 10.35h	<p>EURAXESS initiative.</p> <p>Slaven Misljencevic EURAXESS Policy Officer – European Commission</p>
10.35h – 10.55h	<p>The Charter & Code (C&C) and Human Resources Strategy for Researchers (HRS4R).</p> <p>Michele Rosa-Clot HRS4R Portfolio manager – European Commission</p>
10.55h – 11.05h	Break
11.05 – 11.55h	<p>Joint discussion of event participants and the EURAXESS representatives, projects coordinators and representatives of national authorities responsible for research.</p> <p>This discussion session will be enriched from the participation of Ivana Radonova, from the Ministry of Education and Science of Bulgaria, and Mark de Vos, EURAXESS Bridge Head for Denmark.</p> <p>The following main discussion points will be addressed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Synergies between the EURAXESS initiative (and in particular the C&C and the HRS4R) and the implementation of gender equality plans. • Relevance of gender equality measures as element to attract researchers and for engaging researchers in a mobility experience.
11.55h – 12.00h	Conclusions and event closure